

Effect of Study Skills Training on The Reduction of Examination Anxiety of Secondary School Students in Enugu Education Zone

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone, Enugu state. Two research questions and two hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. Quasi-experimental research design was adopted for this study. The population for this study was a total of 724 comprising of all SS II students from co-educational secondary schools in Enugu education zone. The sample size for the study comprised eighty (80) SS II students with high level of test anxiety (40 male and 40 female). The instrument, Test Anxiety scale (TAS) adapted from Sarason (1980) was used for the identification of students with high examination anxiety. Data collected from the study were analyzed using mean and ANCOVA. Results obtained from the study indicated that SST is really an effective treatment in reducing examination anxiety among secondary school students. The reduction in examination anxiety of female students was more than male students after treatment. The study also found a significant differential effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of male and female secondary school students in Enugu education zone. Based on the findings of this study, some recommendations were noted. The researchers recommended, among others that school counsellors should apply study skills training on reduction of examination anxiety students as it has been proved to be effective on it.

Key words: Study skills training, examination, anxiety, reduction

Introduction

Poor academic performance is a difficult and never-ending problem that parents, educators, and society as a whole must deal with. Performance is a byproduct of learning at all stages of academic pursuit, and it is influenced by a variety of factors present at the time of learning as well as those present between learning and application (Enyi, 2009). Students whose academic performance falls short of their abilities have been the focus of considerable attention and research, making poor academic performance one of the most serious problems and a major worry in today's schools and institutions.

The main reason for schooling is to facilitate learning, though learning takes place every now and then and at any place; these forms of learning are mostly unconscious. Since learning outcomes cannot be observed directly, the individual has to be assessed to ascertain whether the necessary skills and facts taught by teachers are learnt. One of the major forms of this assessment is examination. It is an underlying assumption in schools that examination will be given. Moreover, Nigeria as a nation recognized examination as the measure of academic attainment of students within the school system. Examination, being an assessment to measure one's knowledge about what he/she had learnt, generates a lot of worry and fear as the person cannot pin down which aspects of the learned topics will be posed to him/her. This fear and worry because of the unknown is known as examination anxiety.

The term anxiety has become commonly used, and it is defined as a general feeling of worry and apprehension in which a person anticipates some horrible event that is not objectively predictable based on his actual situation (Nwamuo & Ihekwa, 2014). Anxiety, according to Bufka and Barlow (2009), is an emotional state in which people experience worry, concern, or fear. People typically experience anxiety when confronted with situations they cannot control or foresee, or when confronted with events that appear menacing or hazardous, such as a medical emergency, a vehicle accident, divorce, failure, or death.

Most people experience some level of anxiety during an examination. However, when anxiety begins to affect examination performance it becomes problematic. Nwamuo (2014) asserted that there are some students who are brilliant but may perform woefully due to some factors within the cognitive processes which are caused by situational factors and internal factors (traits) which consequently result to anxiety or phobia disorder. Almost everyone has confronted such a feeling of anxiety throughout the course of life. Learners at different educational systems experience great ranges of anxiety. Their anxiety is sometimes so excessive that it disturbs their educational and daily performances. One of the significant types of anxiety is "examination anxiety" which has embraced great deals of research in the field of education (Oladipo & Ogungbamila, 2013; Yazdani & Soleimani, 2011).

Examination anxiety is defined by Olatoye and Afuwape (2013) as a candidate's psychological state of mind concerning an examination as reflected by the level of worry, dread, uncertainty, concern, and helplessness expressed before, during, or even after an examination. Exam anxiety, according to Ergene (2003), is a scientific construct that refers to a combination of phenomenological, physiological, and behavioural responses that accompany fear of negative consequences or failure during an examination or other evaluative circumstance. When the capacity to complete a task is evaluated, unpleasant emotions, experiences, or fears contribute to a decline in coping abilities in various scenarios, such as examination taking, and hence to examination anxiety (Cheraghiyan, Moghadam, BarazPardejani & Bavarsad, 2008). Negative cognition, attention deficits, improper physiological reactions, and poor educational achievement are the most common outcomes (Abolghasemi, 2005). For the purposes of this study, examination anxiety is defined as the presence of psychological stress that results in intense fear, worry, and concern during an examination.

Examination anxiety is an educational problem that is commonly experienced by all students. Practically, students will feel some level of anxiety when they take an examination, but for some students the level of anxiety increases drastically and affects their performance (Abolghasemi, Mehrabizadeh, Najjarian & Shokrkon, 2006). Examination anxiety as a common and significant phenomenon in education, involves the combination of physiological over-arousal, worry and dread about examination performance and frequently disturbs the normal learning and also decrease the examination performance (Yousefi, Ma'rof, Mariani, Rumaya, & Mansor, 2010).

Examination anxiety is an emotional problem which if not attended to, could result in neurotic difficulties (Adeola & Adedipe, 2007). A person suffering from examination anxiety can be described as one who knows the material but the intensity of their anxiety and excitement prevent him from reflecting his knowledge in the examination session (Fathi & Imamgholivand, 2005).

Various therapy and training strategies have been used to deal with this form of anxiety, including relaxation, stress inoculation, biofeedback, and psychological therapies, each of which has a varied effectiveness on examination anxiety (Karami & Milani, 2004). Examination anxiety was previously thought to be a physiological or emotional phenomenon. Treatment efforts at the time were focused on using behavioural approaches to reduce physiological arousal. Later, the focus of treatment changed to cognitive and combined approach (Akca, 2011). Behavioral therapies integrating systematic desensitisation, relaxation training, biofeedback, modelling, anxiety reduction technique, anxiety management training, and other behavioural techniques have been developed or applied to examination anxiety (Kondo & Gifu, 1997). Cognitive techniques such as rational emotive therapy, cognitive restructuring, and other cognitive techniques, as well as cognitive-behavioral techniques such as cognitive-behavioral modification, stress-inoculation training, and other cognitive-behavioral techniques (Beck, Emery & Greenberg, 1996). Study skills training, examination-taking skills training, other skill deficit treatments, and a combination of cognitive behavioural and skill-focused treatment approaches are all utilised to treat skill deficits (Ergene, 2003).

Study skills are discrete techniques that may be taught and used to all or most fields of study in a short period of time. As a result, they must be distinguished from techniques that are specialised to a certain area of study and qualities that the student possesses (Gruber, 2011). Dunnin Ossai (2012) defines study skills as the process through which each learner begins to concentrate, absorb, and recall challenging knowledge. A student might study in a variety of methods to improve his capacity to retain information and think critically. Mnemonics, effective note taking, effective time management, summarising, and the usage of key words are some of the categories. There are a variety of additional ways to learn such as memorization, communication skills, flashcard training, condensing material, summarising, using keywords, acronyms, and mnemonics, exam tactics, effective time management, organisation, and life style adjustments are examples of such ways (Parker, 2010).

Study skills training has been used to examination anxiety with recorded successes among adolescents (Karfe, & Ntasin, 2018; Ngwoke, Ossai & Obikwelu, 2013; Ossai, 2012). Although, there are a number of research works on test anxiety in Nigeria, for instance, Osiki and Busari (2006) have used self-statements monitoring techniques in reducing test anxiety among adolescent underachievers, while Karfe, and Ntasin, (2018), have successfully used systematic desensitization therapy and study skills training in the reduction of test anxiety in Physics among senior secondary school students in Nigeria. It is based on the above evidence of study skills training in treating examination anxiety, that the researcher wants to determine effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria and Enugu State in particular, students have been consistently performing below average in various secondary schools especially in external examinations. The academic underachievement of students within the Nigerian education system has been attributed to several factors including school curriculum, study skills, students' academic self-concept and teacher expectations. This has been a source of worry to the various stakeholders such as teachers, educational psychologists, parents, students and society at large.

In recent times, the stakeholders such as the parents, educationists and government as well as the media have raised alarm about the deteriorating standard of education and increased examination malpractice in Nigeria. While some people blame the educational system, some blame teachers and the teaching methods and others blame the students for their inability to read and comprehend what have been taught. Moreover, only few people could associate the problem to emotional maladjustment, which seems to be plaguing students as a result of the sensitivity in the developmental stage. There is inherent fear and anxiety resulting from high expectations from parents, paper qualification expectations and adjustments in terms of sexual role. In order to meet up with these expectations, these pupils could be caught in the grip

of fears and anxieties. These situations when applied to testing may not make for high academic performance. It is against this background that the researcher sought to determine the effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State.
2. The differential effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of male and female secondary school students in Enugu education zone, Enugu state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

1. What is the effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State?
2. What is the differential effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of male and female secondary school students in Enugu education zone, Enugu state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant effect of skills training on examination anxiety of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State.
2. There is no significant differential effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of male and female secondary school students in Enugu education zone, Enugu state

Methodology

The study adopted the quasi-experimental research design. The design is called quasi-experimental because it does not employ randomization in the placement of participants into experimental and control group. The population of the study is 724 students. These comprised of all SS II students from co-educational secondary schools in Enugu education zone with high level of test anxiety. The sample size for the study comprised eighty (80) SS II students with high level of test anxiety (40 male and 40 female). For even representation, non-proportionate stratified random sampling procedure was used to draw two secondary schools from each of the three Local Government Areas in the zone. A total of six (6) schools were drawn. A purposive sampling technique was used in selecting two secondary schools because they have the highest number of students with high level of test anxiety.

The instrument, Test Anxiety scale (TAS) adapted from Sarason (1980) was used for the identification of students with high examination anxiety. The items in TAS were scored on four-point rating scale of: Always (4), sometimes (3), Rarely (2), Never (1). The instruments "Test Anxiety scale (TAS)", was subjected to face and content validation. The researcher presented copies of the questionnaire together with purpose of the study, research question and hypotheses to three experts, – two from educational psychology and one from measurement and evaluation all of whom are from Enugu State University of science and Technology, Enugu. The experts made careful scrutiny of the items to ensure their appropriateness and adequacy as well as their relevance, clarity and language expression. The experts' constructive criticism and suggestions for modifying the instruments were affected in an effort to standardize the instrument.

The reliability of the instruments was established for Nigeria settings through internal consistency estimate. Participants involving 100 students from secondary schools in Anambra State were selected through accidental sampling technique. The researcher used Cronbach alpha statistical method in determining the reliability coefficients of the instruments. The reliability coefficient of Nigerian Samples yielded 0.81. This was considered high enough to be used for this study.

Procedure for Data Collection

Students with high scores were considered to be having high test anxiety and were assigned to both the experimental and control groups. A special request was made to the school principals for the provision of adequate and conducive centre for the administration of the questionnaire. The Test Anxiety scale (TAS) was administered to the students in the chosen schools for this study by the researcher, with the help of two research assistance. The research assistances collected the Test Anxiety scale (TAS) from the respondents and handed over to the researcher for scoring; the results of the first administered Test Anxiety scale (TAS) made up the pre-test scores. All responses for the Test Anxiety scale (TAS) were be summated to yield a total score.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected for this study were analyzed using mean in answering the research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Experimental Procedures

The researchers visited the chosen schools, solicited for the cooperation of the principals so as to build in the programme in the schools' activities. The researchers explained the purposes and benefits to be derivable from the treatment to the principals of the schools. Prior to the commencement of the treatment, Test Anxiety scale (TAS) was administered on the students in the experimental and control group. The examinations were administered by the research assistants with the researcher monitoring the exercise, to make sure that the examination was taken under the same conditions and then collected the entire completed questionnaire.

The researcher administered the experimental treatment, while the research assistants in control group handled the control group and administer copies of the questionnaire. The treatment was designed to last for 6 weeks using the normal school timetable that allocated 45 minutes for guidance and counselling. A total of six sessions were used for the experiment. The control group was exposed to conventional counselling with the school counsellors providing the services to the students with high examination anxiety. This also continued for 6 weeks, and then the students were post-tested.

For the experimental group, study skills training was designed to last for 6 weeks. Each session started with the introduction to the issues to be addressed in the session and sample questions to elicit students' participation in the session.

After the treatment, the Test Anxiety scale (TAS) was re-administered to the experimental and control groups. The instrument was disguised by reshuffling before they were re-administered. This was done by the 6th week. The researcher monitored the exercise to ensure that the students are under the same conditions and then, collects all completed questionnaire. The student responses were scored and data generated were collected for statistical analysis.

Control of Extraneous Variables

The researcher was much aware of the possible effect of extraneous variables which if not well controlled could have polluted the study and distort the findings. As such, some efforts were made to ensure that these pollutants were reduced to minimum, such effort to control the extraneous variable include:

1. One of such strategies is the use of separate schools in this experiment for the therapeutic treatment. That is, experimental and control groups were located at different schools to avoid subject interaction and contamination.
2. Administration of treatment is another dimension in which there is control of extraneous variable in each school. All students received the same treatment program except for the control group in the same conditions.
3. The researchers are aware of the Hawthorne effect. The Hawthorne effect according to Macefield (2007), is an experimenter effect whereby participants, in the study may exhibit atypically high levels of performance simply because they are aware that they are being studied, and thus changes in participants' behaviour during the course of a study. The measures put in place to avoid this are: The researchers used the first week trying to familiarize himself with the pupils to avoid the student faking their behaviour. The items in the post-examination instrument were reshuffled.
4. Use of analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA): some extraneous variable may still remain uncontrolled, in spite of the measure the researchers must have put in place. Such possible gaps were taken care of through careful application of the analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) in data analysis, thereby isolating the distorting variable as covariates.

Results

Research Question one: What is the effect of study skills training (SST) on examination anxiety of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State?

Table 1: Pre-test and Post-test examination anxiety mean Scores of Students Treated with study skills training (SST) and those in the Control Group

Source of Variation	N	Pre-test Mean	Post-test Mean	Mean lost	Remarks
SST	40	99.38	58.81	40.57	Effective
Control	40	97.47	94.15	3.32	

Research question one shows that the students treated with SST had pre-test mean score of 99.38 and post-test mean score of 58.81 with mean loss of 40.57 in their examination anxiety scores, while the students in the control group who received conventional counselling had pre-test mean score of 97.47 and post-test mean score of 94.15 with mean loss 3.32. Therefore, SST was effective on examination test anxiety of secondary school students in Enugu education zone.

Hypotheses One: There is no significant effect of skills training on examination anxiety of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State

Table 2: ANCOVA on the Pre-test and Post-test examination anxiety Mean Scores of Students Treated with study skills training and those in control group

Source of Variation	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	MS	Cal. F	Crit.F	P ≥ 0.05
Corrected Model	25629.687 ^a	2	12814.844			
Intercept	1894.633	1	1894.633			
Pretest Scores	97.976	1	97.976			
Treatment Models	21677.468	1	21677.468	221.252	3.94	S
Error	10653.304	77	109.767			
Total	933965.000	80				
Corrected Total	46272.992	79				

Table 2, showed that at 0.05 level of significant, 1df numerator and 119df denominator, the calculated F 221.252 is greater than the critical F 3.94. Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected. So, there was significant difference in the effects of SST on examination anxiety of students when compared with those in control group.

Research Question two: What is the differential effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of male and female secondary school students in Enugu education zone, Enugu state?

Table 3: Pre-test and Post-test examination anxiety Mean Scores of Male and Female Students Treated with study skills training

Source of Variation	N	Pre-test Mean	Post-test Mean	Mean lost	Remarks
MALE	20	99.43	65.07	34.36	
FEMALE	20	101.52	59.57	41.95	More Effective

Table 3 revealed that male students treated with SST had pre-test mean score of 99.43 and post-test mean score of 65.07 with a mean loss 34.36, while the female students in the group had pre-test mean scores of 101.52 and post- test mean score of 59.57 with a mean loss of 41.95. Therefore, SST was more effective on the examination anxiety of female students than their male counterparts.

Hypotheses Two: There is no significant differential effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of male and female secondary school students in Enugu education zone, Enugu state

Table 4: ANCOVA on the Pre-test and Post-test examination anxiety Mean Scores of Male and Female Students Treated with study skills training

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	Cal. F	Crit.F	P ≥ 0.05
Corrected Model	35619.687 ^a	2	17809.844			
Intercept	1993.733	1	1993.733			
Pretest Scores	153.279	1	153.279			
GENDER	34677.678	1	34677.678	380.85	4.03	S
Error	10653.304	37	91.054			
Total	933965.000	40				
Corrected Total	46272.992	39				

Table 4, showed that at 0.05 level of significant, 1df numerator and 39df denominator, the calculated F 380.85 is greater than the critical F 4.03. Therefore, the second null hypothesis is rejected. So, there was significant difference in the Pre-test and Post-test examination anxiety Mean Scores of Male and Female Students Treated with study skills training

Discussion of Findings

The findings in showed that study skills training was effective on reduction of examination anxiety of secondary school students in the treatment group when compared to those in the control group. Specifically, the finding indicated that students in both experimental and control group had high examination anxiety before the commencement of the study as measured by their score on the pre-test. The finding also indicated that the magnitude of the mean difference between the experimental and control group was significant in the post-test. The first hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test examination anxiety mean scores of students treated with SST and those in the control group was rejected. It implies that SST significantly reduced examination anxiety of secondary school. The study is in line with Ossia (2012) who concluded that Study skills have no significant influence on students' test anxiety levels. The finding also corroborates with Karfe, and Ntasin, (2018) that students who received study skills counselling therapy experienced less test-anxiety than those who did not. The study further agrees with Otta and Ogazie (2014) whose findings revealed that study skills technique was effective in reducing test-anxiety of students. However, the findings of this study is contrary with the findings of Ngwoke, Ossai and Obikwelu (2013), whose study reported that study skills had no significant influence on students' test-anxiety.

The findings further indicated a significant difference in the Pre-test and Post-test examination anxiety Mean Scores of Male and Female Students Treated with study skills training. In particular, the reduction in examination anxiety of female students was higher than that of male students after they had participated in SST treatment. This suggests that female students benefited more from SST than female students did. The result in hypothesis two which stated that there is no significant differential effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of male and female secondary school students in Enugu education zone, Enugu state was rejected. This findings disagrees with that of Ogbu in Karfe, and Ntasin,

(2018) whose findings reported that male students obtained higher mean score on test-anxiety than females, meaning that the academic achievement of female students were higher than their male counterparts, since it is assume that, the higher the test-anxiety the lower the academic achievement of students.

Conclusion

The study investigated the effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of secondary school students in Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State. In accordance with the findings of this study, the following conclusions have been drawn: That SST is really an effective treatment in reducing examination anxiety among secondary school students. As such, its usage should be encouraged. The reduction in examination anxiety of female students was more than male students after treatment. The study also found a significant differential effect of study skills training on examination anxiety of male and female secondary school students in Enugu education zone.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. School Counsellors should apply study skills training on reduction of examination anxiety students as it has been proved to be effective on it.
2. Governments and school administrators should provide adequate support to school counsellors and teachers alike, by providing conducive environment and giving adequate incentives to boost counselling activities in schools.

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